

EUREKA

European Knowledge Repository for Best Agricultural Practices

Join us in developing the EU Farmbook!
A user manual for adding digital ‘knowledge objects’ to the online platform

Version 1.0

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1 Introduction

1.1 A few words about the EUREKA project and its vision

Every year, numerous multi-actor projects (MAPs) run under the umbrella of European Research and Innovation funding. They generate valuable practical knowledge for farmers, foresters, advisors, and other practitioners but currently these outputs are spread out across a number of project websites in many different forms and often remain unknown and unused by potential end-users.

The EUREKA project (<https://h2020eureka.eu/>) brings together organizations from 15 European countries with a wide range of expertise related to the rural sector (SMEs, universities, NGOs, etc.). The goal of the project is to **test the feasibility** of making the increasing volume of practice-orientated knowledge generated by EU-funded research and innovation projects **available to farmers, foresters, advisors and other practitioners** via an **attractive, easy-to use, interactive, multi-lingual online EU-level digital platform**.

EUREKA has constructed a **pilot knowledge reservoir** which is called the 'EU FarmBook'. It is searchable and has multiple user-friendly features to help ensure the longer-term and wider use of the fantastic knowledge and innovative solutions generated by multi-actor projects. We now **need your support** to populate the digital platform with as much information (so-called 'knowledge objects') as possible to a) test its functionality and useability and b) start building the foundation of this extraordinary long-term knowledge resource.

Find out more about the EUREKA project by watching the [EUREKA introductory video](#) and by following us on [YouTube](#) and [Twitter](#).

1.2 What is this user manual for?

This user manual explains in clear and concrete terms how to upload digital files ("Knowledge Objects") to the pilot version of the EU FarmBook.

*"A **Knowledge Object** contains useful, practical information about best and innovative practices in agriculture."*

1.3 Who is this user manual for?

This manual is primarily intended for the partner organisations actively involved in **Horizon 2020 multi-actor projects** (already completed or still in progress) who are in a position to **share the publicly-available digital outputs of their projects**. At the same time, this does not exclude other EU-funded initiatives that are generating or collecting practice-orientated digital material (e.g. within the day-to-day work of the National Rural Networks or EIP AGRI) from also contributing to the pilot EU FarmBook.

Please note that this user manual **does not** address the potential for connecting existing databases or knowledge platforms (e.g. those under development in some Member States) to the 'EU FarmBook'. For further guidance on this issue please contact the project coordinator, Prof. Pieter Spanoghe, at pieter.spanoghe@ugent.be.

How to read this user manual?

You can use this manual if you are a digital technology novice, an expert user or anything in between! We want to ensure that everyone is able to make their material available through the 'EU FarmBook'.

We recommend continuing the reading of the manual from Section 2 and Annex-I to learn about the **FAIR data principles**, and why they are important in an open collaborative scientific community.

Section 2 also explains the **categories of digital material** that can be shared through the 'FarmBook'.

Section 3 provides details about **how to upload your digital material** to the FarmBook. The Annex-III to V provides some additional information.

2 Sharing agricultural knowledge

2.1 Why sharing material about agricultural best practices?

Farmers have always shared and compared knowledge about the best available agricultural practices. The EU Farmbook makes this more possible in a digital age. Researchers have discovered that the more research outputs they share – whether publications, presentations, videos, data sets or anything else – the more their research is appreciated, and the more impact it has. Everyone benefits!

In recent years, there has been a big movement for “Open Science” and the “multi-actor approach” and this is very much supported by the European Commission and all research institutions. The FAIR data principles are a practical side of this movement, whilst the multi-actor approach specifically encourages the co-creation of knowledge and innovation by connecting researchers and practitioners (e.g. farmers, foresters and their advisors) much more closely in projects that address the real needs that exist in practice.

2.2 Metadata – what is it?

The FAIR principles depend on the use of **metadata**. Metadata is information *about* a knowledge object like publication, presentation, data set, and so on (for more details about knowledge object, see section 2.4 and Annex-III). So, the *author* of an article is a piece of metadata (data about data). The date of publication is a piece of metadata. It is important that metadata is easily read by machines (computers) so as to be able to index knowledge objects, help people find them, or collect them into groups. So, metadata is usually **formally** represented in a structured way for example as here:

Title: A paper about the Farmbook
Author: Christopher Brewster
Date of publication: 2021
URI: <https://www.somewhereontheinternet.com/paper>

Figure 1: Structure of basic metadata

To better understand what this information is about and what it can help with, consider the case of a book. The **title of the book**, the **name of the author(s)**, the **name of the publisher** and the **year in which the book was published** are metadata for the book (in other words, additional information describing the book).

The users of the EU FarmBook do not need to completely understand metadata, but they will use it all the time. People who add items (“Knowledge Objects”) to the FarmBook need to have some metadata ready at hand (e.g. the author of a document) so as to fill in the form which capture the relevant metadata.

The way in which metadata (the additional information for a “Knowledge Object”) will be supplied through the form is explained in **Section 3**.

Figure 2: Practical information of what “metadata” is about

2.3 Explaining the FAIR principles

The acronym FAIR¹ stands for **F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable, and **R**eusable. Put (very) simply this means²:

- **Findable**: Make sure a knowledge object can be found and found again.
- **Accessible**: Make sure a knowledge object can be accessed (for example by downloading it) and that access is given to the appropriate person or system.
- **Interoperable** (more relevant for data but not only): Make sure that the knowledge object is represented or annotated in a way that allows it to be combined with other Knowledge Objects or data sets.

¹ Wilkinson, et al. (2016). The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. Scientific Data, 3, 160018. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

² <https://www.force11.org/group/fairgroup/fairprinciples>

- **Reusable:** Make sure the Knowledge Object has suitable metadata explaining who by and how the Knowledge Object can be used (for example whether commercial use is permitted).

Because the FAIR data principles apply both to the Knowledge Objects themselves, as well as the metadata about the Knowledge Objects, this means that it is a good practice to use standard vocabularies (“ontologies”) to describe the Knowledge Object or data set, refer to a standardised license regarding reuse, as well as to keep the metadata available (ideally in a permanent way) even if the Knowledge Object is no longer available.

It must be stressed that the FAIR data principles are not mandatory, rather they are a set of principles the scientific community is aspiring to put into practice to facilitate knowledge exchange. Also, the principles are not an obligation to make everything freely or openly available; it is rather a good practice to describe Knowledge Objects systematically.

More details about FAIR data shared in the **Annex-I**.

2.4 What is a Knowledge Object?

This document is a **step-by-step guide for submitting digital material** to the pilot EU FarmBook to make it available to other people interested in agricultural best practices. In the FarmBook, we refer to this digital material as “Knowledge Objects”. A **Knowledge Object** contains useful, practical information about best and innovative practices in agriculture. As shown in Figure 3, there are several categories of Knowledge Objects and a detailed list of examples shared in the Annex.

Figure 3: The categories of Knowledge Objects considered for the “FarmBook”

2.5 Preferred formats of Knowledge Objects

As highlighted earlier, there are various categories of Knowledge Object (e.g., **documents, spreadsheets, slideshows/presentations, videos, podcasts, images, software applications, and datasets**). Each Knowledge Object could be available in various **formats**.

In this section, we provide a list of **preferred file formats** for the Knowledge Objects. These file formats have been selected having in mind **what is the most popular software** for accessing the content of the Knowledge Objects (remember the *Accessible* principle).

To better understand what we mean with the term **format**, you may take a look at the **Information Highlight box** on the side, and the example provided in Figure 4 below.

INFORMATION HIGHLIGHT

A **file format** is the way in which information is encoded in order to be made available as a computer file.

There are **many different types of file formats**, which depend on the information provided with the help of a computer file.

We also distinguish between **file formats for proprietary software** (i.e., software that the user needs to pay for) and **file formats for free-to-use software**.

Figure 4: An example of the format of a digital file that is a document

Figure 5 shows some well-known and widely-used file formats.

Figure 5: Examples of well-known and widely-used file formats for documents, spreadsheets, and presentations

The **preferred** Knowledge Object **formats** for submitting Knowledge Objects to the EU FarmBook are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Examples of file formats for “Knowledge Objects”

“Knowledge Object” type	Recommended formats	Acceptable formats
Textual data	.rtf, .txt, xml	.html, .doc/.docx
Tabular datasets	.por, .csv, .tab	.sav, .dta, xls/.xlsx, .mdb/.accdb, .dbf, .ods
Image data	.tif	.jpeg, .jpg, .jp2, .gif, .tiff, .raw, .psd, .bmp, .png, .pdf
Presentation	.ppsx	.pptx, .pdf
Audio data	.flac	.mp3, .aif, .wav
Video data	.mp4, .ogv, .ogg, .mj2	.avchd
Geospatial data (vector and raster data)	.shp, .shx, .dbf, .prj, .sbx, .sbn, .tif, .tfw, .dwg, .gml	.mdb, .mif, .kml, .ai, .dxf or .svg
Documentation and scripts	.rtf, .pdf, .xhtml, .htm, .odt	.txt, .doc/.docx, MS Excel .xls/.xlsx, .xml

3 Getting Started

Before uploading a Knowledge Object to the FarmBook we need to provide some additional information about it (this is the **metadata** as **file formats** mentioned earlier). This information will help other people **search** and **find** the Knowledge Objects they are interested in, and consequently will help promote your own work to others. To do so, a **step-by-step example** is provided in the next section and more details about each sub-section of the FarmBook web upload form shared in the **appendix-III**.

3.1 The EU FarmBook

The pilot EU FarmBook has been created to help achieve the main goal of EUREKA – to test the feasibility of ensuring that the **outcomes of the EU-funded multi-actor projects** will continue to exist after the end of the projects. The primary focus of the pilot FarmBook is upon multi-actor projects funded under Horizon 2020 – whether already completed or on-going. If the pilot FarmBook proves to be a success then it will be developed further under the 2021-2027 Horizon Europe research and innovation programme.

The EUREKA project has built the pilot EU FarmBook to not only allow **the searching for and finding of material**, but **also the uploading** digital content.

This manual is about the uploading of content, but firstly it’s important to understand a little more about how the FarmBook works. The first page of the “FarmBook” is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: The first page of the EU FarmBook

3.2 An example of submitting a Knowledge Object to the EU FarmBook

In this final section, we provide a concrete and complete example of the information (the metadata) that need to be provided to submit a document to the EU FarmBook platform (and make it available through it).

The document is a **factsheet** developed in the AFINET³ Thematic Network. This document is shown in Figure 7 below.

³ You may find out more about AFINET by clicking on [this link](#).

Given that our Knowledge Object is a document, this is the Knowledge Object category (i.e., “Document”) that we need to select from the dropdown list shown in Figure 8 below.

The **title of the document** (as it appears on the first page) is:

“PRODUCTIVE USE OF THE TREE ROW UNDERSTOREY”

By following the title tag on data upload web form, the document title should be typed (in the respective field of the FarmBook form) as follows: “**Productive Use of the Tree Row Understorey**”.

Figure 9 shows exactly how the document title should be typed into the respective field of the FarmBook form.

Apart from the title, providing a **short textual description** of what the content of the document is about (a summary of the document’s content) will allow for a quick overview.

This summary is the following (just an example):

“*This document is a factsheet created in the context of the AFINET project that gives information about opportunities for crop diversification.*”

Figure 7: An example of a document to be submitted to the FarmBook platform

The way of typing this short summary into the respective field of the form is shown in Figure 10.

Category & Type

The category that best fits the type of the supplied knowledge object

-- select an option --

Please provide a value for this field

Category & Type

The category that best fits the type of the supplied knowledge object

-- select an option --

- ✓ Document
- Slideshow/Presentation
- Video
- Podcast
- Image
- Software Application
- Dataset

Please provide a value for this field

Figure 8: Selecting the category of our example Knowledge Object from the respective dropdown list

TITLE*
PRODUCTIVE USE OF THE TREE ROW UNDERSTOREY

The title of the knowledge object

Figure 9: Typing the title of the example Knowledge Object in the respective filed of the EU FarmBook form by following the naming guidelines described in Subsection 3.3.

DESCRIPTION*
This document is a factsheet created in the context of the AFINET project.

A short (500 character or around 100 words) summary of the knowledge object.

Figure 10: Typing the description of the example Knowledge Object in the respective filed of the FarmBook form

The document is also available in the Zenodo digital repository, which means that there is already a DOI assigned to it. The DOI of the factsheet is “**10.5281/zenodo.3585495**” and the way to provide (as a piece of metadata) to the submission form of the FarmBook is shown in Figure 11 below.

Knowledge Object

Yes, I will provide the URL to the object

KNOWLEDGE OBJECT URL*
<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3585495>

the URL to the knowledge object

Figure 11: Providing the DOI of the example Knowledge Object in the respective field of the submission form of the EU FarmBook

The document has been created in AFINET. The full **name** of the project is “**Agroforestry Innovation Networks**” and **AFINET** is the **acronym** used for reasons of simplicity. The **link** to this project’s website is <https://agroforestry.net.eu/afinet/>. These are the final pieces of information needed to be provided as part of the process of submitting the Knowledge Object to the FarmBook. The way to make this information available is illustrated in Figures 12, 13, and 14 respectively.

PROJECT NAME*
Agroforestry Innovation Networks

The project under which the knowledge object was created

Figure 12: Typing the full name of the source project into the respective field of the EU FarmBook platform

PROJECT ACRONYM*
AFINET

The acronym of the project under which the knowledge object was created

Figure 13: Typing the acronym of the source project into the respective field of the FarmBook platform

PROJECT URL*
<https://agroforestry.net.eu/afinet/>

The main URL of the project under which the knowledge object was created

Figure 14: Typing the link to the source project's website into the respective field of the FarmBook platform

As we have already explained earlier the type of knowledge object, next to that the selecting and providing **sub-type** of knowledge object (see, Figures 15).

Document Type

-- select an option --

should be string

+ ADD ITEM

Document Type

Brochure

↑ ↓ −

✓ -- select an option --

Article in conference proceedings

Book

Booklet

Brochure

Chapter in edited volume

Deliverable report

Factsheet

↑ ↓ −

+ ADD ITEM

Figure 15: Selecting the type of the “Knowledge Object”

The keywords associated to this document (to be provided as input) are **“diversification”**, **“silvoarable”**, **“tree row”**, **“crops”**, and **“understorey”**. The way to provide them, by considering the guidelines described in Annex-III and is shown in Figure 16.

Keywords

Please provide a list of keywords indicative of the content of the object

diversification

silvoarable

tree row

crops

understorey

+ ADD ITEM

Figure 16: Typing the keywords associated with the “Knowledge Object” into the respective field of the form by following the guidelines presented in Subsection 3.3

The name of the **creator** of the Knowledge Object is **Maria Rosa Mosquera-Losada** and the **language** in which its content becomes available is **English**. The supply of these pieces of information in the FarmBook submission form is shown in Figures 17 and Figure 18 respectively.

Creators

Provide the name(s) of the creator(s) of the object

Figure 17: Typing the name of the “Knowledge Object” creator into the respective field of the form

Languages

Please provide the language(s) in which the knowledge object is available. In case translations of the object are separate files or pages, please handle each translation as it's own object.

Figure 18: Selecting the language in which the content of our example “Knowledge Object” is available

The next thing to do is to provide the **license** type under which the Knowledge Object has become available. This license type makes explicit the way(s) in which the Knowledge Object can (and needs to) be (re-)used by any interested parties. In the case of our example Knowledge Object, the license under which it is made available is “[CC BY 4.0](#)”. We may “inform the system” about this specific license type by making the appropriate selection from the respective dropdown list (or by directly typing in the link to the respective license description) as shown in Figure 19.

License

Figure 19: Providing the license type under which the “Knowledge Object” is made available from its source

Selecting and providing as input the **type**, and the **intended purpose** of the document is what comes next. The document is of the type “**factsheet**”. The purpose of the document’s creation is “**communication**”. Providing this information by making use of the FarmBook form is done in the way shown in Figures 18 and 20 below.

License

Figure 20: Selecting the potential action that the Knowledge Object” may be used for

The document was **created** on the **1st of March, 2018 (01/03/2018)**. The **link to the source** from which the document has been retrieved is “https://euraf.isa.utl.pt/files/pub/20190529_factsheet_14_en_web.pdf”. The way to provide these pieces of information about the specific Knowledge Object is shown in Figures 21 and 22 respectively.

Completion Date

Figure 21: Providing the date of creation of the “Knowledge Object ”_Year

Completion Date

Day of Completion

The day on which work on the knowledge object was completed

Figure 22: Providing the date of creation of the “Knowledge Object”_Date

Our Knowledge Object describes solutions related to crop diversification, which have been tested in **Spain** and **Portugal** (as made evident from the descriptions provided in the document). So, the names of these two countries should be selected from the dropdown list as the input needed to be provided in the “**Geographic Location**” field. The way to do this is illustrated in Figure 23.

Geographical Location(s)

Please select all countries referenced in the knowledge object's contents.

The interface consists of two vertically stacked dropdown menus. The first dropdown menu contains the text 'Spain' and a small downward arrow icon. To its right are three dark green buttons: an upward arrow, a downward arrow, and a minus sign. The second dropdown menu contains the text 'Portugal' and a small downward arrow icon. To its right are three similar dark green buttons: an upward arrow, a downward arrow, and a minus sign. Below the second dropdown menu is a dark green button with a white plus sign and the text '+ ADD ITEM'.

Figure 23: Selecting the countries mentioned in the document as the geographic locations where the provided solutions have been tested

The last step before uploading our Knowledge Object in the EU FarmBook platform is to define its **subject**. Assigning subjects to our Knowledge Object is **a process that takes place in two steps** as shown in Figure 24. In the case of our example, the subjects that can be assigned to the Knowledge Object at Step 1 (“High Level Subjects”) are “Forestry” and “Environment” (more than one subjects can be provided). The subject to be assigned at Step 2 (“Specific Subjects”) is “Farming/forestry competitiveness”. To provide input regarding the Knowledge Object’s subjects (and let the system “know” what our Knowledge Object is about), we just need to **make the appropriate selections** from the respective **dropdown lists** provided in the EUREKA upload form.

High Level Subjects

Please select the most appropriate high level subjects.

⌵ ↑ ↓ —

⌵ ↑ ↓ —

+ ADD ITEM

Specific Subjects

Please select the most appropriate specific subjects.

⌵ —

+ ADD ITEM

Figure 24: Selecting the subjects being addressed in the Knowledge Object

Annex-III provides additional information about each step of the upload process on the EU FarmBook that you need to provide together with each of your Knowledge Objects.

Annex-I: FAIR Guiding Principles for data management

As explained in earlier section, the acronym FAIR⁴ stands for **F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable, and **R**eusable. Put (very) simply this means⁵:

- **Findable:** Make sure a knowledge object can be found and found again.
- **Accessible:** Make sure a knowledge object can be accessed (for example by downloading it) and that access is given to the appropriate person or system.
- **Interoperable** (more relevant for data but not only): Make sure that the knowledge object is represented or annotated in a way that allows it to be combined with other Knowledge Objects or data sets.
- **Reusable:** Make sure the Knowledge Object has suitable metadata explaining who by and how the Knowledge Object can be used (for example whether commercial use is permitted).

F

Findability: Data outputs should be discovered by both humans and machines, for instance by being referenced with unique **persistent identifiers** (e.g., digital object identifiers (**DOIs**) and Uniform Resource Identifiers(**URIs**)) and by being added meaningful, machine-actionable **metadata** and **keywords** to search engines and research data catalogues.

In order to make a knowledge object findable, there are two important aspects:

1. Providing in the metadata suitable keywords or linking with appropriate items in a taxonomy. This makes the knowledge object findable by search engines, or users can browse a taxonomy to find items of interest. Figure 25 shows a metadata example for a book and an article.

⁴ Wilkinson, et al. (2016). The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. Scientific Data, 3, 160018. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

⁵ <https://www.force11.org/group/fairgroup/fairprinciples>

Book

Adapting to climate change

Language:	English	Descriptive
Authors:	Peñis, A., (ed.) FAO, Rome (Italy), Forestry Dept., eng	
Publication Information:	Rome (Italy) FAO 2009	
Publication Date:	2009	
Physical Description:	1 website	
Series:	Unasylva (FAO); v. 80	
Publication Type:	Book	
Document Type:	Non-fiction	
Subject Terms:	Forest management; FORESTRY ASSESSMENT; RESOURCE; COI; POLITIQUE FORESTIERE; CHAI; IMPACTO AMBIENTAL; CONSERVACION DE LOS RECURSOS; OF PROTECCION FORESTAL; AFRICA; USA; SOUTH EAST ASIA; BRAZIL; GHANA; EUROPE; AF	Administrative
Notes:	10670 English	
ISSN:	0041-8436	
Online Access:	Access Full Text	
Accession Number:	fao.671674	
Database:	FAO Catalog	

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Rule-based classification and mapping of ecosystem services with data on the integrity of forest ecosystems

By: Srinivas, A.; Srinivas, Pragnan?; Srinivas, W. Srinivas; Weisner, P?

ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract

Background: The study of ecosystem influences on their services for humans, therefore, the description, identification, and measurement of ecosystem conditions and ecosystem services are of the heart of the issue and the broader basis to represent nature and its processes accurately. Following this paper examines the relationship between forest ecosystem conditions and ecosystem services at the national level, using Germany as an example. The aim is to make a methodology that can be used to understand and quantify the potential supply of selected ecosystem services in light of the current and future land use patterns and the influence of climate change on climate change, and that is to provide a method for ecosystem services. In addition, the methodology was applied to a landscape and sub-basin scales. Methods and results: The influence of forest ecosystem systems was grouped into 78 classes according to the degree of integrity of the ecosystem services. The influence of forest ecosystem services, namely, biodiversity, ecological and cultural values, and hydrological and soil conservation services, were also assessed. The potential of ecosystem services were defined for the present and the future landscape. The ecosystem services were mapped for all Germany. Conclusions: The methodology presented a methodology and the results of the study of forest ecosystem services.

Keywords

Author Keywords: Ecosystem condition; Ecosystem integrity; Ecosystem services; Rule-based coding of ecosystem services; 3D; Biodiversity; Biology; Ecology; Environmental systems

Keywords Plus: CLIMATE; FOREST

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Publisher: SPRINGER, ONE NEW YORK PLAZA, SUITE 4800, NEW YORK, NY, ON 10017-1001

Journal Information:

Impact Factor: 3.00 (2006)

Categories / Classification:

Research Areas: Environmental Sciences & Ecology

Web of Science Categories: Environmental Sciences

Figure 25: Metadata example for book and article

2. Providing the knowledge object with a unique identifier (for example a DOI – digital object identifier - for an academic paper, or a URL - web address – for a video). This makes it possible both for humans and machines to *find again* the knowledge object when needed. Figure 26 shows examples of a DOI from different platforms.

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January 1, 2017 Report Open Access

Food security, food safety and climate changes

Vrabcheva, Teri

Access to sufficient safe food is a basic requirement for human health. Ensuring food safety and security in a highly globalized world presents increasingly difficult, and often under-appreciated challenges, for governments, commercial organizations and individuals alike.

Food security is undoubtedly amongst the most pressing of challenges confronting the world in the twenty-first century. The FAO definition (1996) highlights the importance of ensuring that all people have access to safe, nutritious, preferred food, rather than simply ensuring that sufficient food is produced. A large part of food security is assuring the food is safe from a chemical, physical or biological aspect.

According to UN, access to a safe and secure food supply is a basic human right. Everyone needs food and needs it every day either plant sources or animal sources or both. Food safety must be an integral part in the nutrition and food security policies and programs. Food safety and food security are interrelated concepts which have an impact on the health outcomes and quality of human lives.

A key challenge to scale up nutrition, public health and food security/food safety globally is to better leverage existing capacity and research working towards evidence based decisions. Food safety deals with safeguarding the own national food supply chain from the introduction, growth or survival of hazardous microbial and chemical agents. Food safety and food security (food availability) are essential goals that need to be met to protect and improve human health and nutrition.

BG; bg; EFSAfocalpoint@mzh.government.bg

121 views 68 downloads See more details...

Indexed in OpenAIRE

Publication date: January 1, 2017

DOI: **10.5281/zenodo.830453**

Keyword(s): Bulgaria, Opinion, food security, Food safety, Challenges

Digital Object Identifiers

Agricultural Systems

Volume 153, May 2017, Pages 69-80

Review

Big Data in Smart Farming – A review

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Received 2 August 2016, Revised 31 January 2017, Accepted 31 January 2017, Available online 7 February 2017.

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agsy.2017.01.023>

Digital Object Identifiers

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open access

Figure 26: Example of a DOI from the Zenodo digital repository and Elsevier

A user of the EU FarmBook who is submitting a new Knowledge Object will either have a DOI available from a journal or other third party, or the FarmBook will generate one automatically (if none is provided).

Accessibility: Accessibility refers to making sure that the Knowledge Object is available, for example in a digital repository and that this is accessible by machines over the internet (if appropriate with suitable access control).

In order to make a knowledge object accessible, there are three important aspects:

1. The knowledge object should be made available in a digital repository that is accessible by humans and machines (i.e., computers) following a standard protocol. For example, one can access a publication on a journal's website in a standardised way.
2. If needed, "access control" can be provided to limit access to only authorised people or machines. For example, to access some journals, a subscription is needed, or the credentials of the university that holds a subscription to the journal.
3. Ideally, metadata about the Knowledge Object should be freely available (even if the access to the Knowledge Object itself is restricted for some reason).

Accessibility does not mean that **anyone** can have access to the data or the Knowledge Objects (i.e., it is not an obligation for entirely open data). This principle actually recommends that the metadata about the Knowledge Object should be freely accessible.

Interoperability: *The extent to which knowledge objects can be **exchanged**, (re-)used, and*

*interpreted across a wide range of application and systems. This is only possible when **metadata, standards, taxonomies, ontologies, and standard file formats** are used to describe knowledge objects so that the knowledge objects can be interpreted by third parties.*

1. File formats should be the ones widely used by the community. This usually means, for example, "pdf" file formats for documents, "ppt/pptx" for presentations, a few standard video file formats, etc. There are more issues with data. Ideally, data should be available in a format that is easy to reuse but also explicit as to what the data means. Here, xml, rdf-compatible file formats (e.g., "ttl") would be preferable, but "csv" (which is less helpful) the most common format.
2. Metadata about the Knowledge Object or the data set should follow common standards used by the community. This means, using a commonly used taxonomy or vocabulary (often referred to as ontology) in a standard format. An example would be the AGROVOC ontology from FAO, and a standard format might be XML RDF. Interoperability of metadata is not something that the EU FarmBook user needs to worry about since it is handled internally by the system.

Reusability: Archived Knowledge Objects should be made available using standard technical

procedures like user licensing and metadata. This does not necessarily mean that the Knowledge Objects should be openly available to everyone, but rather that information about how the Knowledge Object could (and should) be (re-)used (or not) has to be made available.

Reusability brings together the three preceding principles because the fundamental purpose of the FAIR principles is to make Knowledge Objects reusable. The important aspects of this principle are:

1. **Reuse license:** Make clear the conditions the Knowledge Object is reusable; for instance: for academic research, for teaching, for commercial purposes, etc. You can assign a suitable license to make this clear and explicit. For this reason, there are various types of licenses available in the **Creative Commons framework** (Figure 27).

Figure 27: The types of licenses available in the Creative Commons framework (source: <https://foter.com/blog/how-to-attribute-creative-commons-photos/>)

Figure 28 shows an example of using licenses for Knowledge Objects in practice.

The image shows two screenshots of digital repositories. The top screenshot is from Zenodo, displaying a dataset titled "Predicting Phenotype from Multi-Scale Genomic and Environment Data using Machine Learning and Knowledge Graphs". It shows 6 views and 0 downloads. The license for the files is Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International. The bottom screenshot is from Harvard Dataverse, displaying a dataset titled "Natural Climate Solutions for Canada". It shows 0 downloads. The license for the dataset is CC0 - "Public Domain Dedication". A red box highlights the CC0 license on the Harvard Dataverse page, and a red arrow points from the text "Creative License" to it.

Figure 28: An example of user license attribution from the Zenodo digital repository and Harvard Dataverse. The license type used is [CC BY 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

2. Make clear the provenance of the Knowledge Object; i.e., where it comes from and (if relevant) how, and for what purpose, it has been created for. So, for a Knowledge Object available in the EU FarmBook the provenance of the Knowledge Object can be made explicit with the help of information (i.e., metadata) about the project in which it has been created (e.g., the project's full name, acronym, and URL), the date of its creation, and the purpose it has been created for.

Annex-II: Types of Knowledge Objects

There are different types of “Knowledge Objects” depending on the category they belong to (namely, “Documents”, “Spreadsheets”, “Slideshows/presentations”, “Videos”, “Podcasts”, “Images/figures”, “Software applications”, and “Datasets”).

Documents

Type of Document	Description
Article in conference proceedings	A research paper presented in a conference by one (or more) of its authors; after the conference end, the paper is published in the proceedings of the conference (i.e., an edited volume with all the papers presented in the conference).
Book	A digital version of a book.
Booklet	A digital version of small book or group of pages.
Brochure	A digital document (of limited size in terms of its number of pages) containing pictures and information on a product or a company (or, in our case, a Multi-Actor Project).
Chapter in edited volume	A document presenting research work, which has been included in a book (edited volume) containing chapters from various contributors. This edited volume usually addresses a specific research topic. An example of a chapter in an edited volume is provided here .
Deliverable report	A document used to report the work done in a project as part of one, or more, tasks, which has led to some results.
Factsheet	A document containing detailed information, for the public, about a product or service.
Flyer	A form of paper-based advertisement aimed for wide distribution and typically distributed or posted in a public place, handed out to individuals or sent through the mail. This document type is very close to the “brochure” type.
Handbook	A book including instructions on how to use something or information about a particular subject.

Guide	A book that gives the most important information about a particular subject.
Journal article	A piece of writing documenting the process and results of a research effort, which is published in a scientific journal. An example of a journal article is available here .
Manual	A book giving instructions or information.
Milestone report	A document used to report the work undertaken in a research project, which has resulted in the achievement of a milestone (milestone = a significant stage or event in a development process).
Newsletter	A short official statement or broadcast summary of news issued periodically to the members of a society or other organization.
Policy brief	A policy brief is a concise summary of a particular issue, the policy options to deal with it, and some recommendations on the best option. It is aimed for government policymakers and others who are interested in formulating or influencing policies.
Practice abstract	A document used to disseminate the results of the project in a concise and understandable way to the practitioners. An example of a practice abstract is available here .
Press release	A press release is an official statement delivered to members of the news media for the purpose of providing information, an official statement, or making an announcement. Press releases can be delivered to members of the media physically on paper and electronically.
Review document	A document used with the aim to provide a review of some piece of work (review = a formal assessment of something with the intention of instituting change if necessary).
Report/paper	A document containing accounts on a particular matter, after thorough investigation or consideration, by a person or body. The information presented is usually supported by strong evidence.
Technical/technology article	This is usually a document presenting a technical topic, and typically the article drills down into some low-level of detail.

Technical information/specifications card	A document presenting a list of technical information about a product or service by having the layout of a “card”.
Tutorial	A document showcasing how to use a product or service in a series of steps.

Spreadsheets

Type of spreadsheet	Description
Analysis model	A spreadsheet-based application where a small set of data is calculated from a large set of data, often exported from some other system.
Business process	A spreadsheet used to support a specific kind of a business process.
Calculator	Spreadsheets developed and used for the purpose of performing some sort of calculations.
Decision support tool	A Decision Support Tool or Decision Support System is an application used to support decision-making processes. This type of software applications serves the management, operations and planning levels of an organization and help people make decisions about problems that may rapidly change and that cannot be easily specified in advance.
Projection model	A spreadsheet-based application used to generate a large volume of data from a relatively small set of input parameters. An example case is a financial projection based on a set of assumptions.
Small database	Spreadsheet-based applications developed and used to simulate the operations of a database system. Such spreadsheet applications are used to collect and enable access to data (e.g., contact lists) in a tabular form.

Slideshows/presentations

Type of Slideshow/presentation	Description
Educational/training presentation	A presentation developed and used for educational/training purposes in an educational/training event/session.
Guide	A type of presentation providing information and/or instructions to help a person understand or do something.

<i>Informative presentation</i>	This type of presentation is used to present specific information to specific audiences for specific goals or functions. Informative presentations are often analytical or involve the rational analysis of information. Sometimes they simply “report the facts” with no analysis at all, but still need to communicate the information in a clear and concise format.
<i>Tutorial (similar to guide)</i>	A presentation type providing practical information about a specific subject.
<i>Motivational presentation</i>	A presentation aiming to provide its audience with the incentive to do something specific (e.g. make a decision, take an action, etc.).
<i>Decision-making presentation</i>	A presentation developed and used with the aim to facilitate decision-making purposes. In this case, however, decision-making is facilitated by the display and analysis of facts/data/results does not draw on the emotional factor as in the case of motivational presentations.
<i>Problem-solving presentation</i>	A presentation created and used with the aim to provide help on how to solve a problem.

Videos

Type of video	Description
<i>Vlog</i>	A record of someone’s thoughts, opinions, or experiences that he/she films and publishes on the internet.
<i>Webinar</i>	The video recording of a seminar session that has taken place online (i.e., a webinar).
<i>Guide</i>	A video that gives you the most important information about a particular subject. For instance, a travel guide available as a video or a wine guide available as a video.
<i>Event capturing video</i>	A video recording of an event. As an example, we may refer to the video recording of the consortium meeting of a project (for instance, the video available at https://www.youtube.com/...=EURAKNOSProject).
<i>Tutorial/how-to video</i>	A video showing how to use or do something in a series of easy stages.

Presentation/live talk capturing video	A video recording of a discussion of two or more people (for instance, the video available at https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=uqeqnE7Clr8&ab_channel=OxfordUnion).
Interview video	A video recording of an interview event (for instance, the video available at https://www.youtube.com/...).
Product/feature review video	A video presenting the basic features of an object/product/device (for instance, the video available at https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=OoY7zp8GkLI&ab_channel=MarquesBrownlee).
Documentary video	A video presenting facts and information about a subject. For instance, a documentary video on animal communication (e.g., the video available at https://www.youtube.com/...=Best Documentory).
Testimonial	A video presenting a person's statement extolling the virtue of a product/service or something else (for instance, the video available at https://www.youtube.com/...=EpicProductions%2CLLC).
Question-and-answer video	A video where a person responds to a number of questions posed by a live audience or being made available in another way (for instance, the video available at https://www.youtube.com/...=WIRED).
Case study	A video providing detailed information about the development of a person, group, or thing, especially in order to show general principles (for instance, the video available at https://www.youtube.com/...=NurtureDigital).
Simulation video	A video presenting a model of a real activity or phenomenon, created for training purposes or to solve a problem (for instance, the video available at https://www.youtube.com/...=AnselmoLaManna).
Educational/training video	video that has been developed for educational/training purposes (for instance, the video available at https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dCOojwkWO8c&ab_channel=BlueSkyFilm%26Media).

Podcasts

Type of podcasts	Description
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<i>Educational/training podcast</i>	A podcast that has been developed and used for educational/training purposes in the context of an educational/training event/session.
<i>Event capturing podcast</i>	A podcast created with the aim to record an event. It is an audio documentary of this event.
<i>Interview</i>	This type of podcast aims to provide the recorded interview of some person.
<i>Solo podcast</i>	This is a common type of podcast and it is often used by people who have expertise in a certain area and want to share with an audience.
<i>Tutorial/guide</i>	A podcast providing instructions on how to use a product, or undertake a process, in a series of easy stages.
<i>Commentary</i>	A podcast containing opinions or explanations of an event or situation.
<i>Panel discussion</i>	A podcast recording people gathered together to discuss a topic in the presence of an audience. Panels often include a moderator who coordinates the discussion and sometimes elicits audience questions, with the goal of being informative and entertaining.
<i>Question-and-answer podcast</i>	A podcast used to record the responses of an expert to the questions asked by another person who is in charge of the Q&A session.
<i>On-demand seminar</i>	A podcast that has been created with the purpose to record a seminar/training session. The recorded session is then available to any interested individual on his/her demand.
<i>Audio magazine</i>	A podcast that incorporates a range of different thematic units as a magazine does.

Images/figures

Type of image/figure	Description
<i>Chart/graph</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A chart is a sheet providing information in tabular form. Chart examples are available here. • A graph is a diagram (for instance, a series of one or more points, lines, line segments, curves, or areas) showing the way a variable change in

	comparison to one or more other variables. Graph examples are available here .
Static figure/image	A display of information through various illustration means (for instance, colours, lines, borders, arrows, photographs) that does not employ any motion-related aspects. Examples are available here .
Interactive figure/image	A figure or image that makes use of motion-related aspects. An example of interactive figures/images are the animated gifs .
Infographic	A collection of imagery, charts, and minimal text providing an easy-to-understand overview of a topic. Infographic examples are available here .
Static map	A representation usually on a flat surface of the whole or a part of an area. A diagram or other visual representation that shows the relative position of the parts of something. Examples of static maps are available here .
Interactive map	Interactive map examples are available here .

Software applications

Type of software application	Description
AI software	This type relates to software applications deploying Artificial Intelligence algorithms/models. As an example, we may refer to chatbots or Q&A tools the use of which allows the user to verbally pose queries (e.g., Amazon Alexa).
Business software	This type relates to software developed to support various business processes. As an example, we may refer to software applications used for storing and processing information about business customers. This type of software is usually developed by software development vendors and made available via a license purchase.
Data repository/database	This software application type relates to systems used to store data/information of various types of importance to an organization.
Data analysis software	Software applications used for performing various types of data analysis. WEKA is a well-known data analysis application.
Decision support tool	A Decision Support Tool or Decision Support System is an information system used with the aim to support decision-making processes. This type of software applications serves the management, operations and planning levels of an organisation and helps people make decisions with regard to

	problems that may be rapidly changing and that cannot be easily specified in advance.
Educational/training software	Software applications that have been specifically developed for education and training purposes.
FMIS	The acronym FMIS stands for Farm Management Information System. A Farm Management Information System is a management information system designed to assist agricultural farmers to perform various tasks ranging from operational planning, implementation and documentation for assessment of performed field work.
Game	The term game is used here to refer to a video game developed with the aim to support training and educational purposes. This kind of educational/training video games are termed as serious games. The reason for not including this type into the educational/training software application category is because of their prominent role in educational/training contexts. A serious game is a game designed for a primary purpose other than pure entertainment.
Scientific software	This type includes software applications developed with the aim to support scientific purposes. As an example, we may refer to bioinformatics software.
Simulation	A simulation is a software application developed with aim to deliver an approximate imitation of the operation of a process or system that represents its operation over time.

Datasets

Type of datasets	Explanation
Auditory data	An auditory dataset contains audio-related data.
Crop-related data	Crop-related datasets contain values associated with variables of interest to the growing of crops and crop production.
Geospatial data	According to the Cambridge online dictionary, the term “geospatial” is used to denote data and information identifying where particular features are on the earth's surface, such as oceans and mountains. Thus, a set of geospatial data contains records that have locational information tied to them such as geographic data in the form of coordinates, address, city, or ZIP code.
Graph-related data	The term “graph-related data” is used to denote any dataset available in the format of a graph. There may be various sources from which a graph-based dataset may have originated from. Well known examples of such datasets are Knowledge Graphs. An example of a Knowledge Graph can be found here.

<i>Imagery data</i>	A dataset that has images as its records. These images may show, for instance, plants infected by various diseases, which can be used for precision crop protection applications.
<i>Input-related data</i>	A dataset of this type contains data in various formats, which relate to the inputs applied to a crop.
<i>Network-related data</i>	This dataset type has similarities with the graph-related dataset type given the fact that from a mathematical perspective graphs and networks are defined upon similar theoretical foundations. Network-based data may convey information about network structures such as relationships and interactions among stakeholders in a value chain.
<i>Temporal data</i>	Sets of temporal data contain data that represents a state in time. Temporal data is collected and utilized for purposes such as the analysis of weather patterns and other environmental variables, monitoring traffic conditions, studying demographic trends, etc. Data relating to this type may be collected manually, by using sensors, or generated from simulation models.
<i>Textual data</i>	Textual data originate from plain text. It is an unstructured type of data having the potential to reveal useful insights relating to various variables of interest. Natural Language Processing (NLP) is a continuously growing research field in the domain of computational linguistics that involves research in models and techniques used to process textual data.
<i>Video data</i>	Video data relates to data that can be potentially extracted or relating to video recordings.
<i>Weather/climate data</i>	In the case of this type of datasets, we are dealing with data relating to the weather and climatic conditions affecting a geographic region. This data may become available from weather stations and satellites.
<i>Yield-related data</i>	This type of dataset contains data about the yield of a crop. Historical yield-related data may be potentially used (together with data of other types) to proceed to yield estimations. This type of data has a temporal dimension.

Annex-III: Additional information on each sub-section of EU FarmBook data upload form

In this section we are going to present, in a step-by-step manner, all the additional information that you need to provide together with each of your Knowledge Objects to have them stored and shared through the EU FarmBook.

Category

The supply of the information that needs to accompany a Knowledge Object starts by providing the category it belongs to. The available categories are: “Document”, “Spreadsheet”, “Slideshow/presentation”, “Video”, “Image/figure”, “Podcast”, “Software Application”, and “Dataset”.

You can select the category for your Knowledge Object by making the appropriate selection from the dropdown list that appears when clicking in the field with the label “Category” (see Figure 29).

Step I:

Category & Type

The category that best fits the type of the supplied knowledge object

Please provide a value for this field

Click here to see category and type options

Step II:

Category & Type

The category that best fits the type of the supplied knowledge object

- ✓ -- select an option --
- Document
- Slideshow/Presentation
- Video
- Podcast
- Image
- Software Application
- Dataset

Figure 29: The field of the “FarmBook” form for providing the category of the Knowledge Object

Title

The second piece of information that you need to provide for the Knowledge Object you wish to submit to the EU FarmBook is its title. The title of the Knowledge Object may include one or more words (see Figure 30).

Step I:

TITLE*

The title of the knowledge object
Please provide a value for this field

Type the title of the knowledge Object

Step II:

TITLE*

EU FarmBook User Manual

The title of the knowledge object

Figure 30: The field of the EU FarmBook form for typing in the title of the Knowledge Object

Description

After the title of the Knowledge Object, you may proceed by providing a short textual description of the Knowledge Object. It is the summary of the content of the Knowledge Object. The idea is to help the users of the FarmBook get a quick idea of what your Knowledge Object is about. For example, the description for this user manual would be *“This user manual explains how to upload digital files (“Knowledge Objects”) to the current version of the EU FarmBook”*.

The description will be provided, from your side, in the form of plain text. It should consist of a one sentence description (maximum 20 words, 100 characters).

Figure 31 below shows the field in the form for typing in the description of the Knowledge Object.

Step I:

DESCRIPTION*

A short (500 character or around 100 words) summary of the knowledge object.

Type or add description of the knowledge Object

Step II:

DESCRIPTION*

The EU FarmBook User Manual explains how to upload the digital object/Knowledge Object to the current version of the “EU FarmBook”.

A short (500 character or around 100 words) summary of the knowledge object.

Figure 31: The field of the EU FarmBook form for typing in the description of the Knowledge Object

Keywords

Keywords are a very important piece of information to provide for a Knowledge Object. They are an essential part of making the FAIR principles work. Every time we find ourselves in the position of searching for information on the web, we do so by typing one or more keywords in a search engine.

The keywords to provide for your Knowledge Objects should be selected to be indicative of what the Knowledge Object is about. There is no maximum number of keywords to provide. However, we consider that seven (7) keywords per Knowledge Object at most will be sufficient. To provide the keywords, you should type each of them (in the respective form field) by not using capital letters at all unless the word is the name of a person, organisation, or place. After having typed a keyword, make sure to use the semi-colon symbol (“;”) to separate one keyword from the other. Keywords may overlap with words in the description but should refer to the **content** of the knowledge object.

Figure 32 below shows the field in the form for typing in the keywords needed to be attached to the Knowledge Object.

Step I:

Keywords

Please provide a list of keywords indicative of the content of the object

+ ADD ITEM

Click on add item and add keywords

Step II:

Keywords

Please provide a list of keywords indicative of the content of the object

User Manual

EU FarmBook

MAPS

+ ADD ITEM

Figure 32: The field of the EU FarmBook form for typing in the keywords related to the Knowledge Object

Creator(s)

Each Knowledge Object has been created by one or more individuals; namely, the creators of the Knowledge Object. In the field of the form shown in Figure 33, you should provide the name(s) of the

Knowledge Object creator(s). These are typically the “authors” but may also include other people in more complex knowledge objects (e.g., a video or a laboratory data set).

An individual usually has a first, last, and sometimes one, or more, middle names. Each part of the name should be provided with its first letter being capital. In the case of more than one Knowledge Object creator(s), make sure to use the semi-colon (“;”) character to separate one creator name from the other.

Step I:

Creators

Provide the name(s) of the creator(s) of the object

+ ADD ITEM

Click on add item and add the name of the creator(s)

Step II:

Creators

Provide the name(s) of the creator(s) of the object

Christopher Brewster

Hercules Panoutsopoulos

+ ADD ITEM

Figure 33: The field of the “FarmBook” form for typing in the name(s) of the Knowledge Object creator(s)

Language(s)

The field of the form shown in Figure 34 allows you to provide the language(s) in which the content of the Knowledge Object is available. You will be able to choose a language by making use of the dropdown list. In rare cases (e.g., a video with subtitles) more than one language is needed, in which case you can select more than one language options from the dropdown list and if a Knowledge Object is available in more than one language, it should be uploaded separately for each different language.

Step I:

Languages

Please provide the language(s) in which the knowledge object is available.
In case translations of the object are separate files or pages, please handle each translation as it's own object.

+ ADD ITEM

Step II:

Languages

Please provide the language(s) in which the knowledge object is available.
In case translations of the object are separate files or pages, please handle each translation as it's own object.

English

Dutch

+ ADD ITEM

Click here to add language(s)

Figure 34: The field of the EU FarmBook form for providing the language(s) in which the content of the Knowledge Object is available

Date of creation

By clicking with your mouse in the field of the EU FarmBook having the label “Date of creation”, you will be able to provide the date of creation of the Knowledge Object. You will do so by doing the necessary clicks in the calendar that appears. Figure 35 illustrates the way to provide the date of creation of a Knowledge Object.

Step I:

Completion Date

Day of Completion

The day on which work on the knowledge object was completed

Please provide a value for this field

Step II:

Completion Date

Day of Completion

The day on which work on the knowledge object was completed

March 2018

M	T	W	T	F	S	S
26	27	28	1	2	3	4
5	6	7	8	9	10	11
12	13	14	15	16	17	18
19	20	21	22	23	24	25
26	27	28	29	30	31	1
2	3	4	5	6	7	8

Clear Today

Click here to add date

Figure 35: The field of the EU FarmBook form for providing the date of creation of the Knowledge Object

Permanent Identifier (URL or DOI)

If the knowledge object has an existing permanent location (e.g., in a journal repository), please provide the corresponding URI or DOI. If none is entered, the “FarmBook” will generate a permanent identifier which you can use in future.

In the field of the form with the label “PID”, you will be able to provide the Knowledge Object’s URI or DOI (if any). The example described in section 3.2, explicitly illustrates how to provide this specific piece of information. Figure 36 displays the field in the FarmBook form aimed to be used for this purpose.

Step I:

Knowledge Object

 Yes, I will provide the URL to the object

the URL to the knowledge object

Please provide a value for this field

Step II:

Knowledge Object

 Yes, I will provide the URL to the object

the URL to the knowledge object

Add here DOI/URL link

Figure 36: The field of the EU FarmBook form for providing the link to the “source” from which the Knowledge Object was drawn

License

The Knowledge Object(s) you want to provide to the FarmBook may become available under a specific license that explicitly mentions the ways and terms of use of the Knowledge Object. You may select the license type that applies to your Knowledge Object(s) by making the appropriate choice from the dropdown list shown in Figure 37, or by explicitly providing the link (URL) to the respective license type’s description. In Annex-I (Figure 27), you may find explanations of the different Creative Commons license types. The default recommended license is CC BY (i.e., entirely free as long as attribution is made).

If there is a license that has indeed been attributed to your Knowledge Object(s) but is not available in the dropdown list, you will select the “Other” option. In this case, there is a dedicated field where you need to provide a link (URL) directing to a webpage with the description of the license. Selection of a license or the provision of a link to an external license is mandatory.

Step I:

License

Step II:

License

Add here license type for the Knowledge Object

Figure 37: The field of the “FarmBook” form for providing the license under which the Knowledge Object becomes available

Type

Depending on the category a Knowledge Object belongs to, there are different types to choose from. Choosing the type helps people when they are looking for specific types of knowledge objects (e.g., a video or a data set). These types become available in the dropdown list that appears when clicking in the field of the FarmBook form with the label “Type” (see Figure 38 below). An explanation of the types of Knowledge Objects available per Knowledge Object category is provided in the Annex-II.

Step I:

Category & Type

The category that best fits the type of the supplied knowledge object

Please provide a value for this field

Step II:

Category & Type

The category that best fits the type of the supplied knowledge object

- select an option --
- ✓ Document
- Slideshow/Presentation
- Video
- Podcast
- Image
- Software Application
- Dataset

Add here to add the type of the Knowledge Object

Figure 38: The field of the EU FarmBook form for providing the type of the Knowledge Object

Intended purpose

This specific piece of information is asked with the aim to know the **purpose** a Knowledge Object has been created for. The different categories of purpose are available in the dropdown list that appears when clicking in the field of the form with the label "Purpose" (see Figure 39 below). The selection and assignment of more than one purpose is permitted. An explanation of each category is available in the Annex-IV.

Step I:

License

Please provide a value for this field

Step II:

License

- select an option --
- Access to Data
- ✓ Communication
- Data storage/Processing
- Decision-making support
- Dissemination
- Education/Training
- Evaluation
- Experimentation
- Modelling
- Monitoring
- Prediction/Forecasting

 Click here to add intended purpose

Figure 39: The field of the EU FarmBook form for providing the purpose of use of the Knowledge Object

Subject

A Knowledge Object may be about **one or more subjects**. You can select the subjects that your Knowledge Object is about in two consecutive steps (specifying “High Level Subjects” and “Specific Subjects”) from the dropdown list that are made available in the form’s field having the label “Subject”. More than one subject choice can be made (see Figure 40 below). The example provided in Section 3.2 illustrates the selection the subjects related to a Knowledge Object. A description of the subjects is provided in Annex V.

Step I:

High Level Subjects

Please select the most appropriate high level subjects.

+ ADD ITEM

Specific Subjects

Please select the most appropriate specific subjects.

+ ADD ITEM

Step II:

High Level Subjects

Please select the most appropriate high level subjects.

environment

↑ ↓ -

society

↑ ↓ -

-- select an option --
forestry
livestock
crop farming
economics
environment
✓ society

+ ADD ITEM

Specific Subjects

Please select the most appropriate specific subjects.

Digitalisation

-

-- select an option --
Agro-ecology
AKIS
animal husbandry and welfare
Aquaculture
biodiversity and nature management
Biomass production
climate and climate change

Click here to add high level and specific subject

Figure 40: The field of the EU FarmBook form for providing the subject of the Knowledge Object

Geographic Location

The content of a Knowledge Object may relate to a geographic location. More specifically, the Knowledge Object you are about to submit to the FarmBook could, for example, describe an innovative method for growing potatoes, which has been applied to Belgium and the Netherlands. These two countries are the geographic locations that the content of the Knowledge Object relates to. You can select the geographic location relevant to the content of your Knowledge Object by using the dropdown list that appears when clicking in the respective field (see Figure 41).

Step I:

Geographical Location(s)

Please select all countries referenced in the knowledge object's contents.

+ ADD ITEM

Please provide a value for this field

Step II:

Geographical Location(s)

Please select all countries referenced in the knowledge object's contents.

Spain

↑ ↓ -

Portugal

↑ ↓ -

-- select an option --
Afghanistan
Albania
Algeria
Andorra
Angola
Antigua and Barbuda

+ ADD ITEM

Click here to add geographical location (s)

Figure 41: The field of the EU FarmBook form for providing the geographic location (the country) where the content of the Knowledge Object is placed

Project name, acronym and website

Most of the Knowledge Object(s) that you are going to submit to the FarmBook have been created as the result of the work done in a project, typically an EC funded project. The final pieces of information to provide for the Knowledge Object(s) of yours are the name, the acronym (or short name), and the link to the official website of the “source” project. Alternatively, the project’s contract number may be provided. In that case, the name, acronym, and URL to the project website (if any) will become available by drawing them from the CORDIS website in an automated way.

In the case that the website of the source project does not exist anymore, you may provide the link to the CORDIS online database with information about the project. Figure 42 below shows the fields of the “FarmBook” for typing in the specific pieces of information.

Step I:

PROJECT NAME*

The project under which the knowledge object was created
Please provide a value for this field

PROJECT ACRONYM*

The acronym of the project under which the knowledge object was created
Please provide a value for this field

PROJECT URL*

The main URL of the project under which the knowledge object was created
Please provide a value for this field

Step II:

PROJECT NAME*
European Knowledge Repository for best Agricultural Practices

The project under which the knowledge object was created

PROJECT ACRONYM*
EUREKA

The acronym of the project under which the knowledge object was created

PROJECT URL*
<https://h2020eureka.eu/>

The main URL of the project under which the knowledge object was created

Type the title of the project, acronym and project weblink.

Figure 42: The field of the EU FarmBook form for providing information about the “source” project of the “Knowledge Object”

The Annex section of this user manual aims to provide brief explanations of the predefined values that are associated with some of the metadata (namely, some of the information required to submit each “Knowledge Object”) in order to allow to make the appropriate option.

Annex-IV: Purpose of Knowledge Objects

This metadata property is used to state the purpose for which a “Knowledge Object” has been created. The values that this property may receive are: “access to data”, “communication”, “dissemination”, and “education/training”. In the case of software applications, the value could be “data storage/ processing”, “monitoring”, “modelling”, “evaluation”, “decision-making support”, “prediction/forecasting”, “experimentation”.

Access to data

This is the value that can be provided in the case that the “Knowledge Object” is a dataset (or belongs to another “Knowledge Object” category) and the primary purpose for which it has been developed is to allow access to raw data. For example, a data set about how tomatoes respond to a new fertilizer.

Communication

The value assigned in the case that a “Knowledge Object” has been primarily created for communication purposes. In the context of research projects funded by the European Commission, “communication” is a term that means to *“promote the action and its results, by providing targeted information to multiple audiences (including the media and the public), in a strategic and effective manner and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange.”* For example, a video summarizing a project is usually produced for “communication” purposes.

Dissemination

The value assigned in the case that a “Knowledge Object” has been primarily developed for dissemination purposes. In the context of research projects funded by the European Commission, “dissemination” is defined as *“sharing research results with potential users – peers in the research field, industry, other commercial players and policymakers.”* For example, an academic paper is usually produced for dissemination purposes.

Education/training

The value assigned in the case that a “Knowledge Object” has been primarily created to serve education/training purposes. For example, a training manual or an educational slide deck is usually produced for training purposes.

Data storage/processing

Value assigned in the case of a Knowledge Object that is a software application.

Monitoring

Value assigned in the case of a Knowledge Object that is a software application.

Modelling

Value assigned in the case of a Knowledge Object that is a software application.

Evaluation

Value assigned in the case of a Knowledge Object that is a software application.

Decision-making support

Value assigned in the case of a Knowledge Object that is a software application.

Prediction/forecasting

Value assigned in the case of a Knowledge Object that is a software application.

Experimentation

Value assigned in the case of a Knowledge Object that is a software application.

Annex-V: The subjects of Knowledge Objects

Subjects To be selected at Step 1

Crop farming

The cultivation of plants for food, animal feed, or other commercial uses.

Livestock

The activity of raising domesticated animals in an agricultural setting to produce labor and commodities such as meat, eggs, milk, fur, leather, and wool.

Forestry

Managing and using trees, forests and their associated resources for human benefit.

Environment

The natural environment encompasses all living and nonliving things occurring naturally, meaning in this case not artificial.

Society

People in general thought of as living together in organized communities with shared laws, traditions, and values.

Economics

Economics focuses on the actions of human beings, based on assumptions that humans act with rational behavior, seeking the most optimal level of benefit or utility. The building blocks of economics are the studies of labor and trade. Since there are many possible applications of human labor and many different ways to acquire resources, it is the task of economics to determine which methods yield the best results.

Subjects To be selected at Step 2

Biomass production

Production of the biodegradable fraction of products, waste and residues from biological origin - from agriculture (including vegetal and animal substances), forestry and aquaculture, as well as the biodegradable fraction of industrial and municipal waste.

Aquaculture

Aquaculture is the farming of aquatic organisms, including fish, molluscs, crustaceans and aquatic plants.

Agro-ecology

Agroecology is a holistic and integrated approach that simultaneously applies ecological and social concepts and principles to the design and management of sustainable agriculture and food systems.

Organic farming

Organic Agriculture is a production system that sustains the health of soils, ecosystems, and people. It relies on ecological processes, biodiversity and cycles adapted to local conditions, rather than the use of inputs with adverse effects.

Digitalisation

Use of technology to convert precise data into actionable knowledge to drive and support complex decision-making on-farm and along the value chain.

Farm diversification/new business models

Farm diversification refers to the trend towards gaining income from diverse activities (e.g., agri-tourism, processing of farm products).

Competitiveness

Competitiveness is the ability of the farm to compete and be successful.

Crop rotation/crop diversification

Crop rotation is growing a different crop on a given land area every growing/planting cycle and season. Crop diversification refers to the addition of new crops or cropping systems to agricultural production on a particular farm taking into account the different returns from value-added crops with complementary marketing opportunities.

AKIS

The term Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS) is used to describe the whole knowledge exchange system: the ways people and organisations interact within a country or a region. AKIS can include farming practice, businesses, authorities, research, etc. and can vary a lot, depending on the country or sector.

Farming equipment and machinery

All machines and tools that are used in the production, harvesting, transport and storage of farm products.

Animal husbandry and welfare

The branch of agriculture concerned with the production, management, and breeding of animals.

Plant production and horticulture

Plant production refers to the cultivation of plants for food, feed, fiber, medicinal and cosmetic purposes. Horticulture is defined as that branch of agriculture concerned with growing plants that are used by people for food, for medicinal purposes, and for aesthetic gratification.

Landscape/land management

Land management concerns all operations, practices and treatments used to protect the land and enhance the goods and services provided by the ecosystem that the land is part of.

Pest/disease control

Any measures, practices and strategies applied to prevent the appearance or spread of pests and diseases in plant production or to limit their impact on plant growth, crop yield and product quality.

Fertilisation and nutrients management

Careful management, monitoring and amending of soil fertility to meet crops' needs and to maintain environmental quality.

Soil management/functionality

Management of soil by focusing on differences in soil types and soil characteristics to define specific interventions that are aimed to enhance the soil health and quality for the selected land use.

Genetic resource

Any genetic material of plant and animal origin of actual or potential value for food and agriculture.

Energy management

All practices and measures applied for the efficient and responsible use of energy resources in agricultural production systems.

Supply chain, marketing and consumption

The full chain of activities and network among the actors for the preparation of a product or service starting from the raw material production till the marketing and consumption.

Farm/forestry competitiveness and diversification

Improvement of the competitiveness of the agriculture and forestry sectors, as well as the quality of life in rural areas and encouragement of diversification of economic activities.

Food quality/processing and nutrition

All aspects concerned with processing, preparing, preserving and distributing foods and beverages, their quality characteristics and nutritional value.

Biodiversity and nature management

Management and sustainable development of nature and conservation of diversity within species, between species and of ecosystems.

Waste, by-products and residues management

Managing waste in an environmentally sound manner and making use of the secondary materials they contain.

Climate and climate change

Climate is the average weather in a given area over a longer period of time. A description of a climate includes information on, e.g. the average temperature in different seasons, rainfall, and sunshine. Also a description of the (chance of) extremes is often included.

Climate change is a long-term change in the average weather patterns that have come to define Earth's local, regional and global climates.